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Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City: A Spatial Approach

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- Sylhet;

Abstract: Cultural mapping is a systematic approach to identifying, recording, classifying and analyzing a city's cultural resources. Present urban growth of Sylhet is forced by rapid urbanization due to global economy. This phenomena has a negative impact on existing historic morphology of this city causing identity crisis, cultural gap and ignorance. This is an emerging question of future survival of this city, how the trace of history and culture within the city should be treated. This question goes beyond the local boundary to national scale as most of the historic cities of Bangladesh facing common problem to deal with upcoming challenges of globalization by keeping identity and authenticity. This study is trying to find the way how to trace the cultural footprints of city using spatial mapping method. This research aimed a method for cultural resource assessment of city through spatial mapping .This research summarizes the steps and outcome of cultural mapping process of Sylhet city with future implication. This cultural layer will provide important spatial information for any future urban planning and conservation intervention.

1. Introduction

In recent world, the phenomena of rapid urbanization and transformation of existing cities has put the conservation of culturally significant areas in the core of urban planning. However, the traditional notions of monuments, groups of buildings or cities sections, identifying them as separate entities within a wider urban context, is not sufficient to protect the characteristics and qualities of cultural properties. Therefore, new approaches of cultural heritage documentation and assessment has aroused for better information and communication. Cultural mapping also named as Cultural resource mapping is considered as a fundamental stage for safeguarding local heritage resources of a community. Internationally, Cultural mapping is increasingly being treated as an essential planning and economic development tool in city scale. According to the Municipal Cultural Planning Toolkit for Ontario Municipalities (MCPI, 2011)cultural mapping is defined as:

A systematic approach to identifying, recording and classifying a community's cultural resources. It involves a process of collecting, analyzing and synthesizing information in order to describe and visualize the cultural resources in terms of issues such as links to other civic resources (e.g. transportation, green infrastructure, public gathering spaces), patterns of usage, and unique character and identity of a given community.

Cultural mapping has various uses from national to municipal scale. In city scale cultural mapping identify and record cultural resources within the city which can be applied in future urban planning process in future (Blaisz, 2014). Cultural mapping also helps to grow community awareness by sharing and informing databases with tourists, visitors, local inhabitants. Moreover, cultural build a stronger base of information on cultural resources, which supports culture sector development by strengthening networks and collaboration across a wide range of cultural groups and activities. From a planning perspective, spatially mapping cultural assets using GIS means that information on cultural resources can be spatially mapped to show how resources are distributed – where they are clustered and where there are gaps. It also makes it possible to analyze how cultural resources relate to planning issues across departments.

In terms of cultural resources, Sylhet city has a rich and diverse history over time.Sylhet, a small city located North-Eastern part of Bangladesh, known as the spiritual capital of this country. From thousand years Sylhet is known for a transitional hub of political, cultural, ethnical and religious migration which shaped a unique urban fabric in city morphology. Spirituality of Sylhet deeply influenced by two major stream of religious philosophy of both Islam and Hindu, not in conventional form but in form or Sufism and Vaishnavism which is deeply rooted in spirit of mysticism, humanity and self-consciousness (Choudhury A. C., 1910). These socio spiritual spaces also turned to be the focal point of the city surrounded by public spaces, road network, commercial center through juxtaposition of sacred space and community space. Cultural spaces are a center of cultural transition beyond language, geography and race to shape this sacred land a spiritual identity and symbol of faith. Apart from religious differences these spiritual spaces have common appeal of 'Formlessness' which may be shaped by the philosophy of Sufism and Gauria Vaishnavism (Choudhury R. , 2012). Being a part of modern world, this may be a contrast to the pluralistic image of today's city but historic city like Sylhet represents singular image i.e. the spirituality.This all influenced the growth pattern of the

historic urban landscape of Sylhet. The relationship between spirituality and urban space is an ambiguous one.

Present urban growth of Sylhet is forced by rapid urbanization due to global economy. This phenomena has a negative impact on existing historic morphology of this city causing identity crisis, cultural gap and ignorance about past. This is an emerging question of future survival of this city, how the trace of history should be treated? This question goes beyond the local boundary to national scale as most of the historic cities of Bangladesh facing common problem to deal with upcoming challenges of globalization by keeping identity and authenticity. This study is very relevant to this present scenario, both in national and local context, as it is trying to find the way how. How to explore our past and preserve it for our future generation. This research proposal is a preliminary approach to make heritage count though developing a methodological study to discover historic city and make documentation for future intervention. This study is an approach how state of art methods, international guidelines like UNESCO recommendations can be applied to local scenario. And obviously to develop future plan for preserving the cultural ethnicity of local cities.

Fig 1 Heritage Resources of Sylhet City

2. Assessment and mapping methodology

2.1 Methodological phases:

There have been several examples of cultural mapping projects all around the world which gives a good basis for methodological development for this project. Ian Cook and Ken Taylor shows a good comparative view on different cultural mapping case studies (Cook & Taylor, 2013). Based on available literature on cultural mapping, following methodological phases have been adopted for carrying the research project:

Fig 2 Four step method applied for the research

Step 01: Developing assessment criteria

Before making decisions about the future of a heritage item it is first necessary to understand its heritage values. This leads to decisions that will retain these values in the future. Specific assessment criteria is important to select which cultural assets need to assessed and put into the primary list (Affairs, 2001). In this assessment an item will be considered to be of cultural heritage significance if it meets one or more of the following criteria:

Table 1 Criteria and inclusion guideline for selecting cultural assets

Criteria	Inclusion Guideline
C1 An item is important in the course, or pattern, of the local area’s cultural or natural history	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shows evidence of a significant human activity • is associated with a significant activity or historical phase • maintains or shows the continuity of a historical processor activity
C2 An item has strong or special association with the life or works of a person, or group of persons, of importance in the cultural or natural history of the local area	shows evidence of a significant human occupation is associated with a significant event, person, or group of persons
C3 An item is important in demonstrating aesthetic characteristics and/or a high degree of creative or technical achievement in the local area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shows or is associated with, creative or technical innovation or achievement • is the inspiration for a creative or technical innovation or achievement • is aesthetically distinctive

- has landmark qualities
- exemplifies a particular taste, style or technology

C4 An item has strong or special association with a particular community or cultural group in the area for social, cultural or spiritual reasons

- is important for its associations with an identifiable group
- is important to a community's sense of place

C5 An item possesses uncommon, rare or endangered aspects of the area's cultural or natural history

- provides evidence of a defunct custom, way of life or process
- demonstrates a process, custom or other human activity that is in danger of being lost
- shows unusually accurate evidence of a significant human activity
- shows rare evidence of a significant human activity important to a community

Step 2 : Making listing of cultural heritage resources:

Based on the criteria of step 1, a list of cultural heritage items were made. The list followed the categorization of cultural resource management framework developed by Canadian Heritage council (fig) . All the heritage assets were categorized into 4 major categories shown in table. Total 26 no of item types were selected under major categories shown in table. Project profile aims to understand significance of the project site in terms of heritage and cultural value.

Table 2Major cultural resource categories

CULTURAL RESOURCE CATEGORIES	
01	Cultural Heritage
02	Natural Heritage
03	Festivals and Events
04	Cultural Space and Facilities

Table 3 List of Heritage Items under major categories

01	Cultural Heritage	Item Code
	Architectural Heritage	101
	Historic Monuments/Structures	102
	Vernacular Residential Heritage	103
	Historic Neighborhood	104

	Old Cemeteries	105
	Intangible cultural heritage	106
	Areas with Socio-political Significances	107
	Archaeological Significances	108
	Historic Roads	109
02	Natural Heritage	
	Park and Gardens	201
	Water body	202
	Significant landscape	203
	Area with rich Biodiversity	204
	Agricultural Landscape	205
03	Festivals and Events	
	Areas of Visual Arts Festivals and Events	301
	Areas of Street Festivals and Events	302
	Areas of Cultural Festivals and Events	303
	Areas of Religious Festivals and Events	304
04	Cultural Spaces and Urban Facilities	
	Significant Educational Institutes	401
	Performing Art Centers (theaters, community center)	402
	Religious Institutions (Mosque+Church+Temples+Akhras+Mazars)	403
	Cinemas	404
	Urban Spaces and Event Zones	405
	Aboriginal Cultural Centers	406
	Historic Commercial Zones markets	407
	Museums	408

Step 3: Developing individual project profile:

Developing individual project profile was an important part of this assessment. Each of the sites with cultural heritage significances was documented into a project profile. A common project profile form was developed. This form was used during site survey to collect basic information about the specific site. The project profile identifies the statement of significances of individual assets and existing conditions or states.

Step 4: Mapping of heritage resources:

Mapping practitioners have developed a range of methods that allow for different levels of Sophistication in the spatial cognition of community members, different levels of access to technology on the part of communities and project facilitators. In this research, advanced geospatial technologies such as Global Position Systems (GPS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have been utilized. GPS is the satellite-based system that allows features to be located on a global coordinate system such as latitude and longitude with a high level of accuracy. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are a set of software-based tools that provide a highly efficient means to manage and display spatial information. GIS is an excellent tool for identifying complex relationships within spatial data, relationships that may not be otherwise

easily recognizable. Every heritage resource items was traced with GPS to identify their locations. The proximity of areas were traced over Google street map to map the location.

2.2 Selection of study area

The survey and assessment was limited inside Sylhet City Corporation area. The survey boundary covers an area of total 27.36 sq km including 27wards.Sylhet city corporation area is located in between 24°51′ and 24°55′ north latitudes and in between 91°50′ and 91°54′ east longitudes. It is bounded by Sylhet Sadar upazila on the north,Dakshin surma upazila on the south, Sylhet Sadar upazila on the east, Dakshin Surma and Sylhet Sadar upazilas on the west.

Fig 3 Study Area : sylhet City Corporation

2.3 Data collection method

The data gathered this work comprised of both primary and secondary data sources. Critically important additional data was accessed through the work of the Mapping Working Group consisting of researchers and mapping assistants. A group of experts provided advice and guidance in the listing process to identify important sites of significances.

Background historic research, which includes consultation of primary and secondary sources and historic documents, is undertaken to identify early settlement patterns and broad agents or themes of change. This stage in the data collection process enables the researcher to determine the presence of sensitive heritage areas that correspond to 4 categories. Typically, resources identified during these stages of the research process are reflective of particular architectural styles, associated with an important person, place, or event, and contribute to the contextual facets of a particular place, neighborhood, or intersection.

A field survey is then undertaken to confirm the location and condition of previously identified cultural heritage resources. The field survey is also utilized to identify cultural heritage resources that have not been previously known. Several investigative criteria are utilized during the field review to appropriately identify new cultural heritage resources. Information about individual items were collected through visual inspection and interview with inhabitants or users.

3. Results

Based on the results of the background research and field survey, numbers of cultural heritage resources were identified within the area of Sylhet City Corporation. Table 2 below lists the cultural heritage resources identified in the survey which provides data for mapping of these resources. It should be noted that the cultural heritage resource boundaries, as illustrated on the feature mapping, are estimated based on patterns in the landscape observed during field review and from aerial mapping, given that property parcel data was not available.

3.1 Listing of cultural heritage resources:

Following table lists the final no of resources that was included in mapping and documenting .As mentioned earlier, the list was categorized by 4 major categories and 16 types. It has to be noted that, primary name of list has been gathered from literature review, expert opinion, community workshop .Then more names were included during field survey.

Table 4 Example of Heritage Listing Table

1 CULTURAL HERITAGE SITES				
101 ARCHITETURAL HERITAGE SITES				
NO	CODE	Ward	Area	Name
1	10101	14	BONDOR	KEAN BRIDGE
2	10102	26	ZINDABAZAR	GIRISH CHANDRA DAS HOUSE

3	10103	17	CHOWHATTA	GOUR GOVINDA'S HOUSE
4	10104	15	JAIL ROAD	SYLHET OLD JAIL
5	10105	16	SAGORDIGHI	SHASAN GHAT KALI TEMPLE, DURGA TEMPLE
6	10106	12	KUARPAR	BIDITLAL DAS' HOUSE
7	10107	13	SHEIKHGHAT	JITU MIAH'S HOUSE
8	10108	12	MEDICAL COLLEGE ROAD	ABU SINA HOSTLE
9	10109	16	NAYASARAK ROAD	SYLHET KHAJANCHIBARI
10	10110	16	NAYASARAK ROAD	SYLHET PRESBYTERIAN CHURCH
11	10111		TILAGOR	MC COLLEGE (KALA BHABAN, PRINCIPLE'S HOUSE, LIBRARY BUILDING)
12	10112	14	MIRZA JANGAL ROAD	MANIPURI RAJBARI
13	10113	13	LAMABAZAR	TIN MANDIR (GAMBHIR SINGH'S TOMB)
101 HISTORIC MONUMENTS LANDMARKS				
NO	CODE	Ward	Area	Name
1	10201		KAZIR BAZAR ROAD	ALI AMJAD'S CLOCK
2	10202		KEAN BRIDGE AREA	KEAN BRIDGE
3	10203		CHOWHATTA	CENTRAL SHAHEED MINAR
4	10204		JAIL ROAD	SYLHET KENDRIO SOMOBAY BANK
5	10205		KEAN BRIDGE AREA	CIRCUIT HOUSE

3.2 Developing individual project profile:

As mentioned earlier, each of the heritage resources was assessed to identify their heritage value and statement of significances. Conservation issues like Present conditions, external threats were also documented in short. Information were inscribed in a common form with photographed and preserved. An example of Project profile has been given in fig.

Asset Type	SES Architectural Heritage	Asset Code	0003
1. ASSET INFORMATION			
NAME	GoluChandio Das House		
COORDINATES			
LOCATION	Chidambalur	Ward no.	2
TIME LINE	1918-94	PRESENT OWNER	Customs & Post Department
PRESENT USE	Customs & Post Office	PREVIOUS USE	Residence
USERS	Customs & Post		
2. IDENTITY FEATURES (in Points)		3. CONDITION/ISSUES/THREATS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roof Chopped shade on top Roof with gables Tiled Eave 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> risky for use poor condition of ground roof pattern has been changed 	
4. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE (one or two sentences, why this structure is important)			
The house of GoluChandio Das. The great bengali religious scholar and translator.			
5. PHOTOGRAPHS (Use Captions)			

Asset Type	SES Park and Gardens	Asset Code	0003
1. ASSET INFORMATION			
NAME	Siddhant Park (Jhal)		
COORDINATES			
LOCATION	Court Point, Bombar	Ward no.	14
TIME LINE	2018	PRESENT OWNER	City Corporation
PRESENT USE	Park	PREVIOUS USE	Park
USERS	Public		
2. IDENTITY FEATURES (in Points)		3. CONDITION/ISSUES/THREATS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large green. High boundary wall. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well Maintained 	
4. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE (one or two sentences, why this structure is important)			
Public recreational & relaxation space.			
5. PHOTOGRAPHS (Use Captions)			

Asset Type	SES Significant Educational Institution	Asset Code	0003
1. ASSET INFORMATION			
NAME	M.C. COLLEGE		
COORDINATES			
LOCATION	Tiladon	Ward no.	20
TIME LINE	1988	PRESENT OWNER	GOVT.
PRESENT USE	EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION	PREVIOUS USE	EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION
USERS	PUBLIC		
2. IDENTITY FEATURES (in Points)		3. CONDITION/ISSUES/THREATS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CENTRAL ARCHITECTURE DISMILANT INSTITUTION 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderated 	
4. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE (one or two sentences, why this structure is important)			
FIRST COLLEGE IN TILADYET			
5. PHOTOGRAPHS (Use Captions)			

Asset Type	SES Area of Visual Arts (Painting and Figurative)	Asset Code	0003
1. ASSET INFORMATION			
NAME	THEATER, ART EXHIBITION, BOY WELS.		
COORDINATES			
LOCATION	KAD NALINGA ALLOTORING, REKAM KADAR	Ward no.	2
TIME LINE	1988	PRESENT OWNER	SDC
PRESENT USE	KAD NALINGA ALLOTORING, JINGING ALLOTORING	PREVIOUS USE	ART EXHIBITION
USERS	PUBLIC USE		
2. IDENTITY FEATURES (in Points)		3. CONDITION/ISSUES/THREATS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TWO STOREY BUILDING ADJACENT OPEN THEATER AT BODE POINT, ANABANAZA, WENDE TUREY DISTRICT MANHOLE 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well Maintained 	
4. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE (one or two sentences, why this structure is important)			
CULTURAL PROGRAMME & VARIOUS PUBLIC GATHERING			
5. PHOTOGRAPHS (Use Captions)			

Fig 4 Example: Individual Project Profile

3.3 Mapping of heritage resources:

All the listed resources were mapped in GIS platform with spatial data. A total of 30 maps were created including 4 category maps and 26 resource type maps. Maps used color shapes for each heritage sites. Following Fig 4 represents a map as an example.

Fig 5 GIS map of cultural heritage site inside Sylhet City

Map: 20 Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City (Natural Heritage)

Map Prepared Under Project
 Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City
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Legend

- - - Sylhet_city_boundary
- 201_Park_and_Gardens
- 202_Water_body
- 203_Significant_landscape
- 204_Area_with_rich_Biodiversity
- 205_Agricultural_Landscape

Fig 6 Map Example : Natural heritage areas in Sylhet City

Map: 40 Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City (Cultural Space and Facilities)

1 0.5 0 1
Kilometers

Scale: 1:45,000

Map Prepared Under Project
Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City
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Legend

- - - Sylhet_city_boundary
- 401_Significant_Educational_Institutes
- 402_Performing_Art_Centers_(theaters_community_center)
- 403_Religious_Institutions_(Mosque+Church+Temples+Akhras+Mazars)
- 404_Cinemas
- 405_Urban_Spaces_and_Event_Zones
- 406_Aboriginal_Cultural_Centers
- 407_Historic_Commercial_Zones_markets
- 408_Museums
- 409_Libraries_Book_Market

Fig 7 Map Example : Cultural spaces and facilities in Sylhet City

Map: 30 **Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City (Festivals and Events)**

Map Prepared Under Project
 Cultural Mapping of Sylhet City
 Copyright
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- Legend**
- Sylhet_city_boundary
 - 301_Areas_of_Visual_Arts_Festivals_and_Events
 - 302_Areas_of_Street_Festivals_and_Events
 - 303_Areas_of_Cultural_Festivals_and_Events
 - 304_Areas_of_Religious_Festivals_and_Events

Fig 8 Festival and cultural event sites

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of background historic research and a review of secondary source material, including historic mapping, revealed cultural heritage resources of Sylhet could be spatially mapped and documented through a mythological approach. This research was a preliminary work to develop a method that can be adopted for cultural mapping of Sylhet city. Cultural mapping is a time consuming, robust process need appropriate funding and skilled hands. Lack of enough documents, limited finding and unavailability of skilled professional were major draw backs of this research. In spite of the limitations, researchers has tried to make some point needs to be address to develop a heritage led vision for Sylhet city. Based on this research experience researchers want to make following recommendations for conserving cultural assets in Sylhet city though cultural mapping documentation.

- a. **Community Engagement:** The cultural mapping work undertaken for documenting cultural heritage assets should ensure input from community people. The work has to put in place a mapping system to enable a wide range of stakeholders to update, maintain and continuously expand cultural mapping information. A community-based Cultural mapping collaboration should be established for Sylhet city and terms of reference developed to address issues such as:
 - i) Developing policies and protocols to guide future data collection.
 - ii) Examining opportunities to tap resources to expand and deepen information on cultural resources for access by residents and visitors.
 - iii) Developing policies for community awareness and education and promoting tools visual tools.
- b. **Building & Maintaining a Culture Resource Database:** Building and maintain a cultural recourse database in municipality level is necessary. A city scale cultural heritage management plan should be developed and updated in regular interval. A thorough cultural assessment and developing an interactive digital database will work as long term archive .This database should also be accessible to common people for sharing information.
- c. **City corporation guideline for management:** This is very important to adopt cultural asset preservation and management in city scale along with national one. In Bangladesh, cultural conservation laws only applied in national scale monuments and site where city scale sites are often ignored due to absence of

any policy. Most of the cultural resources in Sylhet city is under ruining and under continuous threat of decay. Imposing preservation laws on heritage properties

- d. Integrating heritage policy with development planning: Recently tourism sector in Sylhet city is playing an important role behind cities economic establishment .Tourism has become an important source of income for inhabitant as well as the city. To develop a tourism led vision for Sylhet city, it is very important to integrate heritage preservation policy with city development and planning. Cultural resources should be taken in to consideration before making decision of future spatial planning and infrastructural development.

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